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Realization of a Low Cost Low Power Acoustic Modem for Underwater Sensor Nodes

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Abstract— This paper describes the realization of a low cost modem for underwater vehicles, sensor networks and biological monitoring systems. This work is focused on the design and implementation of a modem using readily available components. FSK modulator and H-Bridge driver are designed and developed with the help of an ARM microcontroller. The demodulator/receiver is realized using PLL and another ARM processor. By studying the characteristics of the piezoelectric transducer, 74 kHz and 82.5 kHz are used for performing FSK modulation. A power supply for driving the piezoelectric transducer around a low loss boost converter is also developed.

Index Terms —acoustic, FSK, underwater modem, piezoelectric transducer

1. Introduction

There is an increasing demand in the design and deployment of underwater acoustic communication networks. Reliable underwater communication is the need of the hour for a wide variety of applications including autonomous underwater vehicle communication, scientific explorations, water-based disaster prevention and biological monitoring. In order to realize short-range underwater acoustic communication, low cost, low power acoustic modems are preferred. Here a simple modem design is presented using readily available low cost components.

This paper describes the realization of a communication system employing a FSK modem. The transmitter consists of a microcontroller and an H-Bridge to drive the transducer which switches between 82.5 kHz and 74 kHz corresponding to the control input status. A direct sequence spread spectrum (DSSS) technique is applied to the data using PN codes before switching between the frequencies. PN code or pseudo noise code sequence is similar to a random signal but is generated deterministically. This gives resistance to interference, reduces errors and fading due to multipath propagation. The received signal is pre-amplified and fed to a micro PLL and to a microcontroller. Using the same PN code the signal is despread to retrieve the data. The system behavior has been tested in the department underwater testing facility.

This paper describes the design and realization of the modem and its experimental setup in detail and the results

are presented and discussed. Section 2 discusses the existing work in the acoustic modem in terms of cost and power. Section 3 describes the acoustic modem architecture block-by-block. Section 4 gives the experimental setup while the last two sections discuss the results and concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

Underwater acoustic communication has been investigated by many researchers. The major focus in this area is the transmission range, bandwidth utilization, reliability in dealing with multi-path propagation and power consumption.

Aydinlink [1] presents the design, implementation, and testing of a flexible physical layer on reconfigurable modem (Rmodem) platform. This physical layer features quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) modulation, convolutional coding, and recursive least squares (RLS) decision feedback (DFE) equalizer with phase locked loop (PLL). Their board features Texas Instruments TMS320C6713 floating-point DSP chip and TLV320AIC codec. The disadvantage of floating point functionality is high power consumption. Rmodem is intended as a research-based rapid prototyping environment and therefore ease of programming is preferred over low power consumption.

The Micro-Modem by Freitag [2] is a compact, low-power, underwater acoustic communications and navigation subsystem. It has the capability to perform low-rate frequency-hopping frequency-shift keying (FH-FSK), variable rate phase-coherent keying (PSK), and two different

types of long baseline navigation, narrow-band and broadband. A typical application requires 50W during acoustic transmission with an omnidirectional projector.

The GMHT-MP modem [3] is an underwater acoustic telemetry modem presented for ecological research (Eco-sensing) applications and is currently being implemented using the TI F2812 fixed-point DSP device with custom amplifiers, matching networks and transducers. The design was presented based on Walsh/m-sequence signaling in which each bit in an 8-bit long Walsh function is spread by a 7-chip m-sequence. The resulting waveform has a 5 kHz bandwidth for robustness to multipath and achieves a 133 bps data rate with a power consumption of 12Watts.

To bring the concept of long-lived, dense sensor networks to the underwater environment, Wils [4] presents a modem which is of low-cost and low-power and for short-range communications. The prototype directly uses the Mica2 mote, which runs TinyOS and the target price point is such that the modem costs as much as the CPU and packaging, around \$30–100. A cheap, low power acoustic modem for real-time data collection in moored oceanographic applications is proposed by Benson [5]. The Mooring Modem receiver and transmitter are realized using the C6713 DSP boards using a power supply of 12V and the total cost is given as 100\$.

Parsons [6] have proposed the use of software acoustic modems running on generic speakers and microphones to establish acoustic communications for underwater sensor networks. They have designed and experimented with a family of simple software FSK acoustic modems on the generic hardware. The results have

shown that 12bps and 24bps can be used within a 10m range with a constant decoding capability. Since they are employing cheap sensor modules and have lower power consumption, the authors expect the system to promote wider deployments of underwater sensor networks.

3. Acoustic Modem Architecture

Underwater communication is difficult due to factors such as multi-path propagation, time variations of the channel characteristics, small available bandwidth and strong signal attenuation, especially over long ranges. Compared to terrestrial communication, under water communication has low data rates because it uses acoustic waves instead of electromagnetic waves. FSK is the earliest form of modulation used for acoustic communication.

Fig 1. Functional block diagram of the proposed modem

Figure 1 shows the proposed modem functional block diagram. After spreading the incoming digital data using PN code and switching it for FSK modulation by the

dedicated microcontroller, the succeeding H-Bridge drives the transducer. The signal transmitted through the acoustic channel is subjected to multipath errors, fading and interference. At the receiver, signal is preamplified and then fed to the PLL CD4046B. The error signal from the PLL is fed to microcontroller where the despreading is performed to obtain the data.

3.1 Transducer

There are several ways of employing underwater communication but the most common is by using hydrophones. Since hydrophones are expensive, cost effective transducers are preferred. Commercially available low cost fish-finders incorporate transducers which are selected for our design. The transducer characteristics are given in Figure 3. The x axis gives the frequency in kHz and y axis the peak to peak voltage in volts. The plot shows two sidebands at 74 kHz and 82.5 kHz peaks respectively for a centre frequency of around 80 kHz.

3.2 Transmitter

The H-Bridge LMD18200 [7] designed for motion control applications, operating at supply voltage 55V and has switching frequencies 500 kHz is sufficient to drive the transducer. The inbuilt braking feature is useful in eliminating ringing and transient oscillations. The FSK signal is given to the PWM input of LMD18200. A 30V regulated power supply is used in the experimental setup.

A dedicated low power LPC1313 ARM processor operating at 72MHz is used to generate the FSK modulated signal.

Spreading of the information with DSSS technique using 8 bit PN code is performed to reduce the fading effect due to the multipath propagation. By applying the PN code directly to the data, the modulator sees a much larger bit rate, which corresponds to the chip rate of the PN sequence. The required FSK signal is generated using the microcontroller's internal timer module, and by changing the status of one input bit, it can switch between the required FSK frequencies 82.5 kHz and 74 kHz. The transmitter schematic diagram is shown in Figure 4.

Fig 2. Photograph of the piezoelectric transducer widely used in low cost fish finders

Fig 3. Frequency response plot shows the transducer characteristics

The power supply for driving the piezoelectric transducer is designed around a low loss boost converter LM2733. The LM2733 device is a switching converter IC that operates at a fixed frequency of 600 kHz using current mode control for fast transient response over a wide input voltage range and incorporates pulse-by-pulse current limiting protection. The power supply schematic is shown in Figure 4. A standard 3.3V low loss regulator is used to drive the power for other components.

3.3 Receiver

The received signal from the transducer is fed to an op-amp pre-amplifier with a gain around 100 which is then fed to micro PLL CD4046B. The CD4046B PLL [8] is a versatile building block, suitable for a wide variety of applications, such as FM demodulators, frequency synthesizers, split-phase data synchronization and decoding, and PLL lock detection. The PLL consists of a comparator, low pass filter (LPF) and a voltage controlled oscillator (VCO) connected to form a closed loop frequency feedback system.

With no signal input applied to the PLL system, the error voltage at the output of the phase comparator is zero. When an input signal is applied to the PLL, the phase comparator compares the phase and frequency of the signal input with the voltage controlled oscillator (VCO) frequency and generates an error voltage proportional to the phase and frequency difference of the input signal and the VCO. The error voltage is filtered and applied to the control input of the VCO. LPF voltage output varies in a direction that reduces the frequency difference between the VCO and signal-input frequency. When the input frequency is sufficiently close to the VCO frequency, the closed-loop nature of the PLL forces the VCO to lock in frequency with the signal input; i.e., once the PLL is in lock, the VCO frequency is identical to the signal input, except for a finite phase difference.

PLL tracks the incoming signal and the VCO error signal which is proportional to the variations in the signal frequencies is fed to the ADC channel of the microcontroller. The data is compared with

Fig 4. Schematic of the boost regulator and the H-Bridge driver for the transmitter

Fig 5. Receiver transducer output displayed on the oscilloscope

the PN code and based on the percentage of correlation between two the data is retrieved. The receiver schematic is given in Figure 6 and the receiver transducer output is shown in Figure 5. The channel 1 shows the incoming signal at the receiver transducer and the channel 2 is the transmitted digital signal.

4. Experimental Setup

Testing was performed in the underwater testing and evaluation facility (UTEF) in the department. The acoustic test tank is 6m. long, 3.55m. wide and of average depth 3.15m. The communication between the laptop and the modem is provided with serial ports. The experimental setup is as shown in Figure 7.

The experiment was carried out by immersing the transmitter and the receiver transducers in water at a distance of 5.5m. The data is sent over the channel using the serial monitor on the transmitter PC. The transmitter side LPC1313 generates the FSK modulated data spread using PN code. The H-Bridge drives the transducer with the help of the boost regulator. The

Fig 6. Receiver schematic showing the PLL and the amplifier

Fig 7. Experimental setup for hardware implementation of the acoustic modem

receiver transducer feeds incoming data to the preamplifier. The amplified out is fed to the micro PLL CD4046B and microcontroller LPC1313. The recovered data is verified at the receiver using serial monitor.

2.1 W which is very low compared to the existing solutions. A comparison of the proposed modem with existing solutions is given in Table 1.

6. Conclusion

A low power, low cost modem has been designed and successfully implemented using commercially available transducers. Communication has been successfully demonstrated in underwater test facility. The modem is proposed to be tested at larger distances and in the open ocean. This modem can also be used for communication between underwater remotely operated vehicles (ROV) thereby bringing down the cost of the end system.

Table 1. Modem results compared with existing solutions

Modem	Aydinlink [1]	Freitag [2]	Iltis [3]	Wils [4]	Benson [5]	Parsons [6]	Proposed Modem
Modulation	QPSK	FHFSK-PSK	M-FSK	FSK	FSK	FSK	FSK
Data rate (bps)	550	5000	133	600	80	31	200
RX Power (W)	> 5	> 5	>3	> 2.5	> 5	6.5	-
TX Power (W)	> 5	> 5	>3	> 2.5	> 5	24.3	2.1
Distance (m)	16	2-4k	-	50-500	<20	100	Tested in short range

5. Result

The test results are analyzed based on the data received at the serial terminal on the receiver PC. Initially data was sent and the frequency shift for 1 and 0 was verified using CRO and same was cross verified at the serial terminal. Later DSSS technique was applied and data was successfully transmitted up to a data rate of 200 bps. Power consumption at the transmitter is

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